

Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines

Updated Landscape Analysis for
Priority List of Adverse events of special interest:
Part 1: Nipah Virus

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Description of the deliverable	This deliverable provides the methods and results of an updated landscape analysis and priority list of potential adverse events of special interest relevant to Nipah virus vaccine trials
Key words	Guidance document, AESI list, Nipah Virus, Toolbox

DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

SPEAC	Safety Platform for Emergency vAccines
AESI	Adverse Event of Special Interest
CEPI	Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations
NiV	Nipah virus
AEFI	Adverse Event Following Immunization
CIOMS	Council For International Organizations Of Medical Sciences
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
CD	Case Definition
DIC	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation
MVA	Modified Vaccinia
TTS	Thrombocytopenia With Thrombosis Syndrome
VIIT	Vaccine-Induced Thrombocytopenia
r-VSV	Recombinant Vesiculostomatitis Virus
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
SOCV	Single Organ Cutaneous Vasculitis
VSV	Vesicular Stomatitis Virus
MODS	Multiple Organ Dysfunction Syndrome
BC	Brighton Collaboration

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A key activity of SPEAC (Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines) has been to establish lists of adverse events of special interest (AESI) that have potential to occur during Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI) funded clinical trials. The initial landscape analysis for Nipah virus (NiV) AESI was completed in April 2020 and was based on a non-systematic literature review of key articles. Phase II clinical trials are projected to start for two vaccine candidates in late 2025 or in 2026 (Oxford Nipah – ChAdOx1; PHV Nipah – VSV, G protein). The primary objective was to conduct a scoping review of literature published after the previous landscape analysis in order to determine whether any new AESI should be added to the previous AESI list for novel Nipah virus vaccines. No new AESI were identified related to Nipah virus disease, however, vaccine platform-associated AESI have been added: Thrombocytopenia with Thrombosis Syndrome (TTS) and Vaccine-Induced Thrombocytopenia (VITT) related to selected adenoviral vector vaccines; and Single Organ Cutaneous Vasculitis (SOCV) related to Vesicular Stomatitis Virus (VSV) vector vaccine. An updated version of the AESI list is included in Section V – Recommendations and Discussion. A new feature of the list is to include SPEAC recommendations regarding the listed AESI in terms of which should be specified in a clinical protocol (based on the vaccine platform) as opposed to those which should be responded to, should any occur during a clinical trial, with a standard approach to investigation and review. All listed Nipah AESIs have Brighton case definitions and SPEAC companion guides. The online version of the Nipah AESI list, has links to the case definitions and guides, and can be found at the SPEAC website (<https://speacsafety.net/>).

1. Introduction

CEPI contracted the Brighton Collaboration (BC), through the Task Force for Global Health, to harmonize safety assessment across CEPI funded vaccine development. Since inception, a key activity of SPEAC (Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines) has been to establish lists of adverse events of special interest (AESI) that have potential to occur during CEPI funded clinical trials.

Adverse events of special interest

An adverse event following immunization (AEFI) is defined as ‘any untoward medical occurrence which follows immunization, and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with the usage of the vaccine. The adverse event may be any unfavorable or unintended sign, abnormal laboratory finding, symptom or disease.’¹

The source definition of ‘Adverse Event of Special Interest’ (AESI) as described in CIOMS VII² is:

“An adverse event of special interest (serious or non-serious) is one of scientific and medical concern specific to the sponsor’s product or program, for which ongoing monitoring and rapid communication by the investigator to the sponsor could be appropriate. Such an event might require further investigation in order to characterize and understand it. Depending on the nature of the event, rapid communication by the trial sponsor to other parties (e.g., regulators) might also be warranted.”

AESI can be specified in the Program Safety Analysis plan early in product development for safety planning, data collection, analysis and reporting on AESI data, and eventually form the base of AESI analysis in the Reporting and Analysis Plan. AESI may also be used to generate or retrieve background rates prior to vaccine launch and be incorporated in risk management plans.

Vaccine safety needs to be conducted across the entire life cycle of vaccine development, approval and use. It is essential that the approach is harmonized and standardized so that data are comparable across different studies and populations. Thus, while several if not most of the AESI identified as relevant to CEPI vaccine programs are likely to be rare events and may never occur in the context of a given trial, preparations must be made to maximize the utility of vaccine safety data so appropriate risk-benefit decisions can be made.

SPEAC has chosen to identify AESI using 4 main approaches as outlined below. The AESI that were included on the 2020 Nipah virus list are shown for each category below:

1. AESI that have been previously identified with immunization in general:
 - a. Anaphylaxis, thrombocytopenia, generalized convulsion
2. AESI associated with specific vaccine platforms:
 - a. Live vaccine: aseptic meningitis, encephalitis, myelitis
 - b. Vesiculostomatitis virus vaccine platform: acute aseptic arthritis
 - c. Modified vaccinia virus platform: myocarditis
 - d. Pandemic and some seasonal influenza vaccines: Guillain Barré Syndrome
3. AESI that may occur during the clinical course or as a complication of Nipah virus infection due to viral replication or a host response immunopathogenic mechanism:
 - a. Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)
 - b. Pneumonitis
 - c. Encephalitis / Encephalomyelitis
 - d. Aseptic meningitis

- e. Convulsion(s)
- 4. Theoretical AESI based on animal models or in vitro experimental data. E.g., vaccine-associated enhanced disease seen in mouse model of SARS1 and MERS vaccines. Not part of the 2020 Nipah AESI list.

The initial landscape analysis for Nipah AESI was completed in March 2020 and was based on a non-systematic literature review of key review articles ([SPEAC SO1 D2.3 Priority list of AESI: Nipah Virus March 31, 2020](#)). Phase II clinical trials are projected to start for two vaccine candidates in late 2025 or in 2026 (Oxford Nipah – ChAdOx1; PHV Nipah – VSV, G protein). Given the time since the first landscape analysis, an update was planned as part of SPEAC 2.0

2. Objective of this deliverable

The primary objective was to conduct a scoping review of literature published after the previous landscape analysis in order to determine whether or not any new AESI should be added to the previous AESI list for novel Nipah Virus vaccines.

3. Methods

The literature search strategy focused on finding reviews of Nipah virus disease published since the last landscape analysis which was completed in March 2020. The search was done on May 14, 2025 and included articles published on or after January 1, 2019. The specific strategy used was:

("Nipah Virus"[Mesh] OR "Nipah"[ti]) **AND** ("Clinical Trial"[Publication Type] OR "Review"[Publication Type] OR "Systematic Review"[Publication Type] OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type] OR "Clinical Trial Protocol"[Publication Type]) **AND** ("2019/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT]) **AND** English[[lang]

All identified articles were loaded into Covidence where review/summary article title/abstract were screened by one medical expert (B Law). Full text review was done subsequently and relevant data extracted into Microsoft Word for the final set of included articles. The main focus of the review was to include articles with a clinical focus (i.e., descriptive summaries of patient cases, or individual case details) that could identify new AESI not already included on the Nipah AESI list. Additional references were identified from the citation lists of the primary review publications and retrieved for full text review.

4. Results

A total of 93 articles were identified by the literature search. Figure 1 provides a PRISMA diagram for the search results. Title and abstract screening eliminated 48 sources. Among the 45 articles kept for full text screening, 39 had potential to inform the SPEAC/CEPI Nipah digital toolkit (24 with information on geographic distribution, 7 on virology and 16 on vaccines). These were forwarded to the digital transformation team for review.

A clinical focus was identified in 37 of the 45 articles. Full text review was done for all 37 and relevant information extracted into Microsoft Word. All 37 articles were in agreement with the first Nipah AESI list, with two major patterns of illness: pneumonia complicated by ARDS and neurologic presentation, primarily encephalitis. Five review articles mentioned additional complications of Nipah virus disease, i.e., myocarditis⁵⁻⁸ and multiple organ dysfunction⁹, but provided no original data. Search of citations in the five articles yielded an additional 5 articles with potential to provide original data related to unique complications.

Four of the five cited articles with the potential to provide original data on additional complications of Nipah virus disease reported myocarditis and all related to the 2018 Nipah outbreak in Kerala, India.¹⁰⁻¹³ This outbreak included 23 cases (18 PCR confirmed; 5 probable).

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow diagram for literature search for Nipah virus priority AESI

Pallivalappi et al¹⁰ described epidemiology of all 23 cases noting a higher than usual case fatality rate of 91.3% (21 of 23). They also described clinical features for 19 admitted to either of the 2 major hospitals in Kozhikode district. Among these it was noted that 7 had elevated troponins I and 2 had global left ventricular hypokinesia on echocardiogram.

Kumar wrote an editorial regarding the Kozhikode outbreak¹¹ and included details of 19 of the cases noting there were: 7 cases with encephalitis and ARDS; 5 with encephalitis, ARDS and myocarditis; 4 with encephalitis and myocarditis; 1 with ARDS and myocarditis; 1 with ARDS alone; and 1 with a prodromal upper respiratory tract infection only.

Chadni et al¹² studied 12 cases seen first in the emergency room. Of these, 11 had encephalitis and ARDS and 10 died, case fatality ratio of 83.3%. There were 6 cases considered to have myocarditis, all of whom had another significant complication: 1 encephalitis, 1 ARDS, 4 both encephalitis and ARDS. The basis for diagnosing myocarditis was: 4 with elevated troponin I (no specific values provided); 3 with ST-T changes in the initial electrocardiogram and 3 with bedside screening echocardiograms suggestive of left ventricular hypokinesia.

Thulaseedaran et al¹³ provided detailed descriptions of 10 cases, 5 of whom were noted to have features of myocarditis including elevated troponin I (5/5), left ventricular dysfunction (2/5). All 5 cases had prodromal illness with fever for 3-7 days prior to hospital admission. All were diagnosed with ARDS and died within a day or two after admission to hospital.

It wasn't possible to determine the overlap in cases for the four studies cited, but it is clear that the Kerala outbreak involved 23 cases of which 18 were confirmed and there were 7 cases of possible myocarditis based primarily on troponin elevation. Further, all cases of presumed myocarditis were critically ill with ARDS or encephalitis or both, and death occurred very rapidly. While it is possible that myocarditis was a credible diagnosis, it is also possible that the elevated troponins and the left ventricular dysfunction were due to critical illness in the context of respiratory failure (Gibson MC, Morrow D; Elevated cardiac troponin concentration in the absence of an acute coronary syndrome. In: UpToDate, Connor RF Ed, Wolters Kluwer. Accessed on Sept 29, 2025)

Since myocarditis was not documented in any other Nipah outbreaks, and there was another explanation for the findings in the Kerala cases, the evidence does not yet support myocarditis as a singular complication of Nipah infection.

Multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) involving kidney, heart, liver and spleen was raised in a review by Bruno et al⁹ citing a single animal model study and a review by Escaffre et al¹⁴ on pathogenesis of Hendra and Nipah viruses in humans. The latter article was retrieved and reviewed in depth. Viremia was the basis for postulating MODS but there was nothing specific and no human evidence cited. Given the rapid deterioration and high case fatality rate in Nipah infection, MODS, if it occurs, is likely a pre-terminal event. As it stands there is no reason to add MODS to the AESI list.

Table 1 presents the Nipah AESI list focusing on those related to Nipah Virus disease only, based on immunopathogenesis, viral replication or both. Nothing has been added to the AESI listed for Nipah virus disease.

TABLE 1. AESI RELEVANT TO NIPAH VIRUS DISEASE

Body System	AESI	Theoretical Basis for Including AESI		Bright on CD	Brighton CD Companion Guide
		Nipah disease immunopathogenesis	Nipah viral replication		
Neurologic	Generalized convulsive seizure	✓	✓	YES	YES
	Aseptic meningitis		✓	YES	YES
	Encephalitis*		✓	YES	YES
	Myelitis*		✓	YES	YES
Respiratory	ARDS	✓	✓	YES	YES

* Infectious encephalitis, myelitis or encephalomyelitis due to Nipah virus

5. Recommendations & discussion

Table 2 presents the full list of AESI that could potentially occur following candidate Nipah virus vaccines. The AESI listed have been arranged by whether or not they are theoretically possible to occur with:

- I. Any vaccine based on host immune response (anaphylaxis, thrombocytopenia, GBS) or vaccine reactogenicity (generalized convulsive seizure).
- II. Any vaccine designed to target Nipah virus (based on Nipah disease immunopathogenesis)
- III. Live-attenuated Nipah virus vaccines (based on complications due to Nipah virus replication). Live attenuated vaccines differ in the degree to which they replicate in the human body as well as in the potential to revert to a version that may behave more like the wild type virus. Pre-clinical and clinical trial data will inform as to the potential likelihood that viral replication could occur and lead to an adverse event.
- IV. Specific vaccine platforms (based on demonstrated platform-AESI association).

It is acknowledged that all listed AESI are rare and unlikely to occur in phase I or II trials. Still, any may occur, and given the associated morbidity and potential for public concern, SPEAC recommends a standard approach to the listed AESI in terms of identifying, investigating, classifying (i.e., meeting or not meeting a case definition) and reporting.

Protocol-specified AESI are defined as those for which an association has been demonstrated with the same or a similar vaccine platform or the antigen(s) included in the vaccine. SPEAC recommends that developers provide specific plans, in the protocol and associated documents as needed, for the approach to all protocol-specified AESIs. Based on existing Brighton case definitions and Companion Guides, SPEAC is developing tools that can assist developers in their protocol plans for the AESI. These could include conducting surveillance during the clinical trial, training site investigators, investigating any possible occurrences including special laboratory testing if indicated (that could be remote from the study site) and plans for follow-up assessments, reporting and MedDRA coding.

Other AESI in Table 2 below are considered theoretical possibilities that could occur with any vaccine, or that are predicted based on Nipah disease immunopathogenesis. As with protocol-specified AESI, the events are admittedly rare and unlikely to occur in early phases of Clinical Trials. Despite that, SPEAC recommends that a standard approach be taken to such events so that there is consistency in classifying and reporting them. This recommendation is aligned with CIOMS VI¹⁵ that noted “Medical and scientific judgement should be exercised in deciding whether expedited reporting is appropriate in...” non-SAE situations.

SPEAC recommendations clearly do not supplant or replace Regulatory obligations. Further, developers may decide to specify more of the AESI in their clinical protocols, than recommended in Table 2 below. Rather it is intended that SPEAC supports developers in taking a standard approach to the listed AESI by providing tools, including Case Definitions, Companion Guides (that contain background incidence rates, risk factors, data collection forms and algorithms for assigning level of diagnostic certainty), online capacity for automated Brighton Classification as well as dashboards for background incidence, evidence on vaccine-AESI associations and non-vaccine AESI risk factors. Further, SPEAC is currently developing additional tools (symptom checklists, AESI laboratory/imaging checklist to determine site capacity for investigating possible AESI and assigning level 1, 2 or 3 diagnostic certainty) to aide clinical trial sites in recognizing and investigating possible AESI.

TABLE 2. SPEAC recommendations for handling theoretically possible AESI according to vaccine type. AESI list for a given vaccine candidate will include all AESIs listed under I and II as well as those for the specific platform, as appropriate (III & IV)

Vaccine type		I. All vaccines	II All Nipah Vaccines	III. Live Nipah Vaccines	IV. Specific Vaccine Platforms	
Theoretical Basis for AESI		Host immune response or vaccine reactogenicity	Nipah disease immunopathogenesis	Nipah virus replication	ChAdOx 1	r-VSV
Body System	AESI	SPEAC Recommendation for AESI				
		Adopt standard approach to investigation and classification, IF occurs as an AEFI			Specify in Trial Protocol	
Dermatologic	SOCV					
Hematologic	TTS-VITT				YES	
Immunologic	Anaphylaxis	YES				
	Thrombocytopenia	YES				
Musculoskeletal	Acute Aseptic Arthritis					
Neurologic	Generalized convulsive seizure	YES	YES ¹	YES ²		
	Aseptic meningitis			YES ³		
	ADEM				YES	
	Encephalitis +/- myelitis*			YES ³		
	Transverse Myelitis ^{&}				YES	
	GBS [#]	YES [#]			YES	
Respiratory	ARDS		YES ⁴	YES ⁴		

* Infectious encephalitis, myelitis or encephalomyelitis due to Nipah virus

& Transverse myelitis with demyelination as opposed to acute infectious myelitis.

GBS has been associated with some seasonal influenza vaccines, monovalent H1N1 pandemic vaccine and COVID-19 ChAdOx-1 S vaccine. It is included in the ‘all vaccines’ column because it has an immunogenic pathogenesis and so is theoretically possible with any vaccine.

¹⁻⁴ Exceptions to table recommendations:

¹ Should be Protocol-specified if vaccine highly reactogenic in terms of febrile response within the first few days following immunization, especially if target population includes children < 6 years old

² Should be Protocol-specified if fever occurs during the known period of vaccine strain viremia (based on animal or clinical data).

³ Should be Protocol-specified if vaccine strain shown to be neurotropic based on pre-clinical or human clinical trials .

⁴ Should be Protocol-specified if pre-clinical data (in vitro or animal models) or nature of human immune response raises the possibility of vaccine-associated enhanced disease.

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2. Definition and Application of Terms for Vaccine Pharmacovigilance. Report of CIOMS/WHO Working Group on Vaccine Pharmacovigilance, 2012, Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences.
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9. Bruno L, Nappo MA, Ferrari L et al. Nipah virus disease: epidemiological, clinical, diagnostic and legislative aspects of this unpredictable emerging zoonosis. *Animals* 2023; 13(159): <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13010159> PMID 36611767
10. Pallivalappil B, Ali A, Thulaseedharan NK et al. Dissecting an outbreak: a clinic-epidemiological study of Nipah virus infection in Kerala, India, 2018. *J Glob Inf Dis* 2020; 12(1): 2127.
11. Ajith Kumar AK, Anoop Kumar AS. Deadly Nipah outbreak in Kerala: lessons learned for the future. *Ind J Crit Care Med* 2018; 22:475-6. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijccm.IJCCM_282_18 PMID 30111920
12. Chandni R, Renjith TP, Fazal A et al. Clinical manifestations of Nipah virus-infected patients who presented to the emergency department during an outbreak in Kerala State in India, May 2018. *Clin Inf Dis* 2010; 71(1): 152-7. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciz789> PMID 31627214
13. Thulaseedaran NK, Kumar KGS, Kumar J et al. A case series on the recent Nipah epidemic in Kerala. *J Assoc Physicians India* 2018; 66:63-7.
14. Escaffre O, Borisevich V, Rockx B. Pathogenesis of Hendra and Nipah virus infection in humans. *J Infect Dev Ctries* 2013; 7(4): 308-311. <https://doi.org/10.3855/jidc.3648> PMID 23592639
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ANNEXES

Annex 1

List of All articles Reviewed for the Nipah Landscape Review

TABLE 1.1. 45 articles retrieved from literature search classified by year published and topic area of interest (marked by ‘YES’). All 37 with clinical content had full text review for possible relevance to Nipah disease AESI. The 39 with possible relevance for digital dashboard topics (Nipah virus geographic distribution, virology or vaccine) were not reviewed but forwarded to digital team. First authors of articles cited in the landscape update are in bold text and the citation number is shown. Full citation for all articles provided following table.

Year Published	First Author	Topic Focus of Interest			
		Clinical Content re Possible AESI	Geographic Distribution*	Virology*	Vaccine*
2025	Branda		YES		
	Ganguly	YES	YES		
	Hafeez	YES	YES		
	Hassan	YES			
	Kim	YES			YES
	Salleh	YES			YES
	Spengler ⁵	YES	YES	YES	YES
	Tyagi	YES			YES
	Yadav	YES			YES
2024	Al-Obaidi	YES	YES		
	Alla ⁶	YES	YES		
	Anish			YES	
	Faus-Cotino	YES	YES		
	Hegde	YES		YES	
	Mishra				YES
	Paliwal	YES	YES		YES
	Saha		YES		YES
	Vasudevan	YES	YES		
Wang ⁷	YES			YES	
2023	Bruno ⁹	YES	YES	YES	YES
	Caruso	YES	YES		
	Diederich	YES		YES	
	Garbuglia	YES			
	Joshi	YES	YES		
	Orosco	YES			YES
2022	Alam	YES	YES		
	Gabra	YES	YES		
	Kummer	YES	YES		
	Quarleri	YES		YES	
	Gomez Roman	YES			YES

2021	Chakravarty			YES	
	Eldridge	YES			YES
	Hauser	YES	YES		YES
	Nikolay	YES			YES
	Singhai	YES			
	Skowron	YES	YES		
2020	Soman Pillai		YES		
2019	Aditi	YES			
	Ambat ⁸	YES	YES		YES
	Banerjee	YES	YES		
	Kenmoe	YES			
	Ochani	YES	YES		
	Sayed	YES			
	Sharma		YES		
	Singh		YES		
Total included articles with relevance to topic:		37	24	7	16
Additional articles found by hand search of included articles					
2020	Pallivalappil ¹⁰	YES			
2018	Ajith Kumar ¹¹	YES			
	Chandni ¹²	YES			
	Thulaseedaran ¹³	YES			
2013	Escaffre ¹⁴	YES			

Listing, in alphabetical order of first author, all articles found in the scoping review of Nipah virus. Articles cited in the landscape analysis are in boldface print, and the 5 articles added from hand search of citations are yellow highlighted.

Aditi, Shariff M. Nipah virus infection: a review. *Epidemiology and Infection* 2019; 147:e95 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268819000086>

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<https://doi.org/10.7861/clinmed.2022-0166>

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<https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciz789> PMID 31627214¹²

Diederich S, Babiuk S, Boshra H. A survey of Henipavirus tropism - our current understanding from a species / organ and cellular level. *Viruses* 2023; 15:2048. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v15102048>

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